

Supporting Information for

Penton blooming, a conserved mechanism of genome delivery used by disparate microviruses.

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Fig. S1. Depiction of Ebor integration within the B10 strain line of *Rhodobacter capsulatus* constructed in 70s and 80s in Marrs' lab (1–8). Each circle represents an individual strain, the name of the strain is depicted with the reference describing the strain origin. The colour of the circle corresponds to a phage presence in the RuBisCO *cbbll* operon, the outline of the circle depicts if the strain was a natural isolate or lab derivative. Asterisks highlight the potential acquisition of Ebor likely from other wild type isolates that were used in the Marrs' lab. Ebor is absent from other sequenced *Rhodobacter* species as estimated by blastn search of nt and WGS databases.

Fig. S2. Images of gels and the water agar plate. a-b) Enzymatic assays of Gp7 with zymogram SDS-PAGE gel (a) and water agar plate (b) shown. BSA and 3C protease were used as negative controls, M15 and Slit enzymes of *Rhodobacter* phage Jorvik (9) as well as lysozyme were used as positive controls. M represents PageRuler™ 10-250 kDa (Thermo Fisher Scientific) marker. c) Gels with LPS samples that were used for Ebor inhibition assay ran on Any kD™ Mini-PROTEAN® TGX™ gradient gel (top) and more diluted samples ran on a 15 % polyacrylamide gel (bottom). The labels correspond to individual strains from which LPS was isolated. M1, PageRuler™ 10-250 kDa (Thermo Fisher Scientific) marker; NR, not relevant; Csp, *Cereibacter sphaeroides*; SB1003, *Rhodobacter capsulatus* strain SB1003; B10, *R. capsulatus* strain B10 Δgta ; M2, Color-coded Prestained Protein Marker, Broad Range 10-250 kDa (New England Biolabs).

Fig. S4. Plaques and cryo-EM images of Ebor samples purified using different techniques. a-c) Ebor^{S120} (left panels) and Ebor^{R120} (right panels) were spotted onto soft agar plates containing host strains B10 (a), SB1003 (b), and SB1003Δ*gtal* (c). d-g) Images of Ebor particles purified using different methods. Ebor^{R120} purified using ion exchange chromatography (d). The particles formed aggregates (green arrows) and the ratio of empty and native particles was close to 1:1. Ebor^{R120} purified using CsCl ultracentrifugation (e), all observed particles were native. Ebor^{S120} purified using sucrose ultracentrifugation (f), all observed particles were empty, the contaminants are likely ejected genome molecules. Ebor^{S120} purified using CsCl ultracentrifugation (g), the particles appear to be releasing their genome. Images were collected at 200 kV using a Glacios TEM equipped with Falcon 4 camera, with the total exposure dose of 50 e⁻/Å².

Fig. S5. Additional structural analysis of the native virion of Ebor. a) Diameters of individual *Microviridae* phages. Central Z slices of the capsids are shown, the densities of phiX174 and SpV4 were generated by ChimeraX molmap command (10) of PDB bioassemblies 2BPA_A and 1KVP_A respectively. For EC6098, a segmentation of EMD-27397 was used, masking out the central virion density for clarity. b) Map of Ebor virion releasing the genome in vitro reconstructed by single particle analysis of Ebor^{S120} virions purified using CsCl gradient. c-d) electrostatic potential of Ebor protrusion (c) and penton (d) estimated according to Adaptive Poisson-Boltzmann Solver (11). The AlphaFold2-predicted (12) protrusion loops shown in the **Fig. 2C** and **Data S3** were connected into a single model with respective subunits of major capsid protein in Coot (13) with the axis of symmetry highlighted (magenta triangle). The colour coding corresponds to the electrostatic potential values of the protein surface calculated at T=298.15K and pH=7.0.

Fig. S6. EMAN2 pipeline (14) applied for the subtomogram reconstruction of the dataset of phage Ebor attached to cells. The colour bar indicates the distance from the centre of the capsid. Different iterations of the refinement algorithm are labelled according EMAN2 conventions: p, 3D particle orientation; t, 2D subtilt translation; r, subtilt translation and rotation; d, subtilt defocus refinement.

Fig. S7. EMAN2 pipeline (14) applied for the subtomogram reconstruction of the dataset of phage Ebor attached to outer membrane vesicles (OMVs). The colour bar indicates the distance from the centre of the capsid. Different iterations of the refinement algorithm are labelled according EMAN2 conventions: p, 3D particle orientation; t, 2D subtilt translation; r, subtilt translation and rotation; d, subtilt defocus refinement.

Fig. S8. RELION pipeline (15) applied for the single particle reconstruction of the dataset of phage Ebor attached to cells. The colour bar indicates the distance from the centre of the capsid.

Fig. S9. Single particle analysis of Ebor^{R120} attached to cells of B10 strain. a-c) C5 symmetry maps of the attached particles classified into class 1 (a), 2 (b) and 3 (c) reconstructed by single particle analysis (SPA). Side view, top view and central slice through y axis are shown from top to bottom, with a central slice through y axis of unfiltered maps reconstructed by subtomogram averaging (STA) shown at the very bottom for comparison. The arrows point at the density of an internal cavity formed above the interacting penton (orange) and the dense disk of the membrane at the site of the attachment (blue). d) Map of full phiX174 (16) in complex with LPS (EMDB 8862). The density of the LPS is superimposed based on the membrane disk visible in panel c) and the colour bar indicates the distance from the centre of the capsid applying to maps in all panels. e) Superposition of maps in c) (orange) and d) (blue). The interacting vertices align.

9ffh fit to native map, residues 10-20

9ffg fit to empty map, residues 10-20

Fig. S10. Structure quality assessment of maps that were used for model building. Fourier shell correlation (FSC) curves of both native and empty particles of Ebor solved by single particle analysis are shown. Examples of a random segment of the model fitting the corresponding maps are shown on the bottom. The FSC threshold 0.143 that is used by RELION for the resolution estimation is highlighted by dashed line.

Fig. S11. Structure quality assessment of lower resolution maps discussed in the article. Fourier shell correlation (FSC) curves were taken from EMD. The calculated FSC was performed by the EMD server based on the provided half maps densities, the author provided FSC corresponds to the output of individual reconstruction software. Half-bit, 0.143 and 0.5 thresholds that are used for the resolution estimation are highlighted.

Table S1. Cryo-EM and ET data collection and processing information.

Parameters	Single particle analysis				Subtomogram averaging	
	native particle	empty particle	genome-releasing	particles attached to cells	particles attached to cells	particles attached to OMVs
Data collection						
Magnification	x120000	x120000	x120000	x42000	x45000	x45000
Pixel size [Å]	1.20	1.20	1.20	2.143	2.50	3.15
Camera (EF) [manufacturer]	Falcon 4 [TFS]	Falcon 4 [TFS]	Falcon 4 [TFS]	K3 (GIF) [Gatan]	Falcon 4i (Selectris) [TFS]	Falcon 4 [TFS]
Instrument*	Glacios, York	Glacios, York	Glacios, York	Krios II, eBIC	Glacios 2, TFS facility, Eindhoven	Glacios, York
Voltage [kV]	200	200	200	300	200	200
Data collection software	EPU (holey carbon)	EPU (holey carbon)	EPU (holey carbon)	EPU (lacey carbon)	Tomo5	Tomo5
Total exposure dose [e-/Å ²]	50	50	50	27.878	117.66	115.9
Exposure dose per tilt [e-/Å ²]	50	50	50	27.878	3.18	1.9
Number of tilts	1	1	1	1	37	61
Tilt span [°]	0	0	0	0	±54	±60
Tilt increment [°]	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	2
Number of acquired micrographs/tilt series	996	1099	2810	2750	42	71
Number of used micrographs/tilt series	954	764	2095	2742	27	25
Defocus range [µm]	0.5 - 2.5	0.5 - 2.5	0.5 - 2.5	0.75 - 3.0	1.5 - 4.0	1.0 - 3.0
Data processing						
Reconstruction software	RELION3	RELION3	RELION3	RELION5	EMAN2	EMAN2
Symmetry	Relion I4	Relion I4	C5	Relion I4, symmetry expansion, C5	icos, symmetry break to C1 and C5	icos, symmetry break to C1
Initial number of particles	5271	3976	6302	75291	1593	1788
Final number of particles	4935	1984	401	class1=18179, class2=2741, class3=2175	c1=1556, class1=295, class2=193, class3=198	c1=1788, weak1=725, weak2=778, strong1=153, strong2=132
Initial model	emd-50356	<i>de novo</i>	emd-50357, emd-50361	emd-50361	emd-50357, break to c1 <i>de novo</i>	emd-50357, break to c1 <i>de novo</i>
Map resolution [Å]	3.2	3.3	24	7.8, 10.4, 13.4	c1=31, far=40†, close=40†, fused=40†	c1=13.2, weak1=25†, weak2=25†, strong1=40†, strong2=40†
FSC threshold	0.143	0.143	0.143	0.143	0.2	0.2
Database entry						
EMPIAR	12148	12156	12153	12168	12170	12185
EMDB	50357	50356	50358	50359	50361	50360
PDB	9FFH	9FFG	NA	NA	NA	NA

*all manufactured by TFS; †low passed to this resolution; EF, energy filter; OMV, outer membrane vesicle; TFS, Thermo Fisher Scientific

Table S2. Raw data related to the Ebor^{R120} inhibition assay.

Sample	OMVs	LPS <i>C.sph.</i>	LPS B10Δgal	LPS SB1003Δgal
biol. rep. 1 buffer [PFUs]	2.00E+10	3.20E+08	3.20E+07	6.00E+07
biol. rep. 1 sample [PFUs]	5.00E+08	3.00E+08	1.50E+06	1.10E+07
biol. rep. 2 buffer [PFUs]	2.00E+10	3.20E+08	6.00E+07	6.00E+07
biol. rep. 2 sample [PFUs]	5.30E+08	2.30E+08	1.70E+07	1.20E+07
biol. rep. 3 buffer [PFUs]	2.50E+09	3.20E+08	6.00E+07	6.00E+07
biol. rep. 3 sample [PFUs]	3.00E+07	3.50E+08	1.80E+07	8.00E+06
biol. rep. 1 RI [%]	2.50%	93.75%	4.69%	18.33%
biol. rep. 2 RI [%]	2.65%	71.88%	28.33%	20.00%
biol. rep. 3 RI [%]	1.20%	109.38%	30.00%	13.33%
average RI [%]	2.12%	91.67%	21.01%	17.22%

OMV, outer membrane vesicle; *LPS*, lipopolysaccharide; *biol. rep.*, biological replicate; *PFU*, plaque-forming unit; *RI*, relative infection

Table S3. Bacterial strains used in this study.

Bacterial species	strain	Purpose	Reference/source
	DE442	source of Ebor	(7)
	SB1003	propagation of Ebor R120, plating strain for inhibition assay	(17)
<i>Rhodobacter capsulatus</i>	SB1003 Δ gtal	capsuleless strain, LPS extraction	(18)
	B10	propagation of Ebor S120, host for cryo-EM experiments	(9)
	B10 Δ gtal	capsuleless strain, LPS extraction	(19)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Stellar	cloning of <i>g7</i>	TakaraBio
	BL21(DE3)	expression of <i>g7</i>	Novagen

Table S4. Model refinement statistics. The values were calculated using wwPDB EM Validation server and Molprobit server (20).

Parameters		Model	
		9FFH	9FFG
Map	EMDB code	50357	50356
	Resolution [Å]	3.2	3.3
Model composition	Non-hydrogen atoms	3473	3379
	Protein residues	451	437
	Residue range	3-192,250-510	3-183,255-510
R.M.S. deviations	Bond lengths [Å]	0.26	0.24
	Bond angles [°]	0.55	0.50
Ramachandran plot	Favoured [%]	96.42	96.07
	Outlier [%]	0.45	0.00
	Z-score	-1.06 ± 0.39	0.08 ± 0.42
Validation	Rotamer outliers [%]	1.83	1.07
	Clashscore	5.05	3.11
	Molprobit score	1.70	1.39
	CaBLAM outliers [%]	3.20	3.00
Atom inclusion*		0.85	0.84

*at the recommended contour level = 0.1

Movie S1 (separate file). Tomogram of Ebor particles attached to outer membrane vesicles formed from disrupted cells of *Rhodobacter capsulatus*, strain B10.

Movie S2 (separate file). Tomogram of Ebor particles attached to the host cell of *Rhodobacter capsulatus*, strain B10.

Movie S3 (separate file). Depiction of the major capsid protein fit into the cropped density of class 1 interacting penton.

Movie S4 (separate file). Depiction of the major capsid protein fit into the cropped density of class 3 interacting penton.

Movie S5 (separate file). Depiction of the Ebor penton blooming, side view.

Movie S6 (separate file). Depiction of the Ebor penton blooming, top view.

Data S1 (separate file). Mass spectrometry analysis of purified virions of Ebor.

Data S2 (separate file). Database of *Microviridae* genomes used for the phylogeny analysis.

Data S3 (separate file). The model of the trimeric protrusion predicted by AlphaFold2.

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